

**A MECHANISM TO PROTECT THE POPULATION IN
EMERGENCIES**

A.P. Akhmedov

Assistant

A.Ch. Norkulov

Trainee-teacher

(Termiz State University of Engineering and Agrotechnology.)

Annotatsiya: Mamlakatimiz hududida joylashgan xavfli obektlarda ishlatiladigan kuchli ta'sir etuvchi moddalarning turlari, ularning inson organizmi va atrof tabiiy muhitga ko'rsatishi mumkin bo'lgan salbiy ta'sirlari hamda ulardan muhofazalanishdagi mavjud muammolar ko'tarilgan. Shuningdek, kuchli tasir etuvchi zaharli moddalarga qarshi kurashning umumiy usullari ko'rsatib o'tilgan hamda ushbu muammolarni bartaraf etishga doir tavsiyalar ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kuchli ta'sir etuvchi zaharli modda, kimyoviy xavfli ob'ekt, konsentratsiya, xavf, zaharlanish, qutqaruv tuzilmalari, razvedka, shaxsiy himoya vositalari, ogohlantirish, muhofaza.

Аннотация: Обострились виды высокоэффективных токсичных веществ, используемых в химически опасных объектах, расположенных на территории нашей страны, их возможное негативное воздействие на организм человека и окружающую природную среду, а также существующие проблемы в их защите. Также были показаны общие методы борьбы с токсическими веществами с сильным действием, а также даны рекомендации по устранению этих проблем.

Ключевые слова: силнодействующее ядовитое вещество, химически опасный объект, концентратсия, опасность, отравление, спасательные сооружения, разведка, средства индивидуальной защиты, предупреждение, защита.

Annotation: The types of highly effective toxic substances used in chemically dangerous objects located on the territory of our country, their possible negative effects

on the human body and the surrounding natural environment, as well as existing problems in their protection have been exacerbated. Also, general methods of combating toxic substances with a strong effect have been shown, as well as recommendations on the elimination of these problems have been made.

Keywords: strong-acting poisonous substance, chemically dangerous object, concentration, danger, poisoning, rescue structures, intelligence, personal protective equipment, warning, protection.

Enter. Among man-made emergency situations, accidents at facilities involving highly toxic substances are distinguished by their high level of losses. In the event of an accident at such facilities, it not only endangers the health of the workers of the facility, but also the residents of the surrounding area. Because they are chemical compounds that have high toxicity and can cause mass poisoning of people and animals under certain conditions (mainly accidents at chemically hazardous facilities), as well as damage the environment. For this reason, there is a need to develop the scientific and methodological foundations of ensuring the safety of the population in the event of such accidents.

The main part of highly toxic substances is transported to enterprises by means of vehicles. If their spillage is observed in the process of transportation or in case of an accident in the objects related to highly toxic substances, the type of substance that has spread, its possible negative effects on the environment and the life and health of people will be determined immediately. and protection methods are used based on the obtained results [3].

For this reason, in the years of independence, the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established as a comprehensive state system for the prevention of emergency situations and action when they occur in our country, and the necessary regulatory and legal framework of the field was formed [1].

Figure 1 Process of working with chemicals

We know that measures to protect workers from chemical poisoning at the facilities are carried out by the service structures of the enterprise, rescuers who are part of the rescue structures. Therefore, every rescuer should be aware of the properties of toxic substances. At the same time, workers and employees who work with toxic substances are also required to know the negative effects of toxic substances on the human body, methods of protection from exposure, types of modern personal protective equipment used for protection against toxic substances, and methods of their use.

Relevance of the topic. The main urgent issue in this field can be caused by training the employees of production enterprises where strong toxic substances are used and the population around the enterprise to act correctly in the event of FV, improving the skills of the enterprise employees and constantly monitoring the settings of the machines. It consists in the lack of development of scientific and methodical bases of prevention of FV or the minimization of its losses, as well as the training of qualified personnel in our country. Also, continuously improving the work done regularly in the field of civil protection; to be able to understand the need for civil protection experts to acquire the methods of advanced practice in a practical way, to systematically master the latest methodological, psychological and other achievements, and to apply them to work practice; rescue work and the need to organize the necessary protection work in order to improve this process, deepen its content and increase its quality determines the urgency of the problem.

The main part. Often, as a result of violations of production technological processes and the rules for the operation of facilities, the spread of toxic substances and the implementation of measures to protect the population from them are required.

Cities and settlements with radiation, chemical and fire hazards, KTEZM, objects with a risk of explosion and biological agents, railway junctions of vehicles transporting substances that have a strong effect on humans, oil and gas fields, the list of oil pipelines, hydro nodes and other objects is clearly presented. Epidemiological, epizootic, epiphytotic and seismically active areas in the disaster area, as well as neighboring areas, places where natural disasters occur, possible damage to industry and agriculture, as well as the number of people in these areas and the amount of estimated losses. is displayed.

Figure 2. The process of elimination of accidents involving powerful substances.

There are several types of strong toxic substances, their physical properties are different, and they have the characteristic of having a negative effect on human body organs through suffocation and respiratory organs. When the human body is poisoned with strong toxic substances, the symptoms of poisoning vary depending on the type of substance. Below we will consider the physical properties and negative effects

of some powerful toxic substances on the human body [3]:

Ammonia.

Ammonia NH_3 is a colorless, suffocating, pungent-smelling poisonous gas. When it affects the human body, first of all, it has a negative effect on the respiratory organs, stuffy nose, cough, difficulty breathing, rapid heart beat, and rapid pulse. Ammonia

vapor causes increased sensitivity of the skin and mucous membranes, itching, reddening of the skin, sore eyes and watery eyes. Its permissible concentration in the air at production enterprises is 20mg/m³. At a concentration of 40mg/m³, people can smell it. If it is 500mg/m³, people will die as soon as they breathe.

Chlorine.

Chlorine - Cl₂ is a greenish-yellow poisonous gas with a sharp suffocating smell. When the human body is poisoned with chlorine, chest pain, tearing, dry cough, nausea, vomiting, loss of balance, shortness of breath are observed. permissible concentration is 1 mg/m³. The minimum perceptible amount of chlorine is 2 mg/m³, and the concentration of 10 mg/m³ has a negative effect on the human body. If its amount in the air is equal to 100-200 mg/m³, it is considered dangerous for a person staying in that place for 30-60 minutes, if its concentration exceeds that, sudden death occurs.

As we have seen above, each chemical toxic substance has a limit permissible concentration. Due to the following factors, an accident at the facilities related to highly toxic substances and the exceeding of the permissible concentration of toxic substances may have a negative impact on the health of the employees of the enterprise and the surrounding population:

- inconvenient location of dangerous objects;
- wear and tear of production means, breakdown;
- increase in the use, storage and transportation of highly toxic substances;
- decrease in the professional skills of workers, labor culture and decrease in qualified personnel;
- irresponsibility of management staff, loss of discipline in production and technological processes;
- insufficient control of the condition of chemically dangerous objects;
- imperfection of the control system of harmful and dangerous factors;
- a decrease in the level of compliance with technical safety rules.

It is important to organize emergency-rescue and other non-delayed work, timely and high-quality reconnaissance work to eliminate the consequences of accidents and

disasters at facilities related to highly toxic substances (KTEZM). . Intelligence is carried out by group units formed from radiation and chemical intelligence structures and performs the following tasks [2]:

1. The location of the accident and the type of toxic substance with a strong effect, as well as the level and extent of poisoning of the area and object are determined
2. The border of the affected area will be bypassed and safe exit routes will be determined.
3. Samples are taken from soil, water and other environmental objects and sent to the laboratory for analysis.
4. The condition of people in the center of the chemically affected area is assessed.
5. As soon as it is determined that KTEZM is spreading to the area or the atmosphere, the workers and employees of the facility and the residents living nearby are informed about the danger.

At the object where the accident occurred, first of all, measures are taken to stop the spill or spread of highly toxic substances, and the boundary of the affected area is determined. Access to this area is not allowed for persons who do not participate in the elimination of the consequences of the accident. This area is surrounded by a special group of workers and servants[3].

Particular attention is paid to hydrometeorological observations to determine the direction of spread of air affected by KTEZMs, safe exit routes from affected areas and the environment. To get out of the accident area, the direction with the shortest wind blowing and perpendicular to the direction of the wind passing through the height is chosen.

Medical assistance will be provided to the injured as soon as possible.

Decontamination of contaminated areas will be carried out after containment of the damaged furnace. KTEZM's neutralizing agents are selected as a source of neutralization of facilities and equipment.

Safety requirements must be observed during the work carried out in the furnace infected with KTEZM, the involved specialists will be provided with a gas mask,

protective clothing and personal protective equipment, and a medicine box. Before starting work in the damaged area, the involved rescuers will be instructed on the type of KTEZM and the situation.

Summary. Nowadays, hundreds of different chemical compounds are used in the production process, agriculture and our life. They are considered harmful to humanity, animal world and flora, and we can see that their number is increasing day by day. Because of this, the risk of possible emergency situations increases. Accumulated experiences in ending the consequences of natural, man-made and ecological emergencies, accidents and tragedies, theoretical knowledge obtained in the protection of citizens, in the above-mentioned FVs, enable citizens to consciously act quickly and decisively, quickly restore economic sectors, will train him to launch and provide timely assistance to the victims. Of course, these tasks are carried out only as a result of a thorough study of the nature, description, causes and consequences of natural disasters, accidents and losses. For this reason, civil protection officers have a huge responsibility (both in wartime and in peacetime) to educate citizens in the spirit of FVs.

A number of laws defining and regulating the interaction of all services involved in eliminating emergency situations of various nature, reducing the scope of losses, preventing or reducing damage to human life and material wealth created by them in Uzbekistan, and Decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers and other regulatory legal documents relevant to the field have been adopted and are being implemented.

Recommendations for further improvement of the system of protection of the population and territories from emergency situations related to highly toxic substances:

1. In chemical hazardous facilities (hereinafter referred to as KXO) replacing toxic substances with less toxic substances or introducing new technologies that reduce the conditions for the release of toxic substances into the air in general;
2. Replacement of outdated technology and equipment with modern ones;
3. Mechanization of production processes. As a result, the labor process becomes easier, the contact of workers with toxic substances is significantly limited.

4. Continuous control over the state of the air environment in the work zone and installation of effective ventilation systems;
5. Placing the KXO in an area far from the residential area;
6. Conduct regular trainings with the employees of KXO, as well as gradually provide them with personal protective equipment.

REFERENCES USED

1. Legal bases of protection of the population and territories from emergency situations (a set of regulatory and legal documents). 1 roof. 9-10 b.
2. R.S. Sobirov. "Extinguishing specific fires in highly toxic and radioactive objects", methodical manual. FMI of the UzR FVV - 2017. p. 15-18.
3. Sharipov A.Kh. "Storage of highly toxic substances in a chemically hazardous facility and in railway transport", methodical guide. Tashkent Institute of Railway Engineers, 2010. p. 13-15.